

Case Study

Examining the Relationship between Organizational Characteristics, Knowledge Management Infrastructure and Entrepreneurial Orientation with Job Communication Satisfaction

Marjan Mousavi¹

Faculty of Humanities, Islamic Azad University, Zanjan Branch, Zanjan, Iran

Abstract

This study investigates the effect of organizational characteristics, knowledge management infrastructure and entrepreneurial orientation on job communication satisfaction in Atieh Sazan Hafez Company. The research was conducted by selecting 102 employees as the statistical sample. The analysis of the present study was performed using the structural equation modeling technique. The results of the analysis of the hypotheses indicated that organizational characteristics help positively and directly with the dimensions of knowledge management infrastructure and entrepreneurial orientation and job communication satisfaction. Efficient and motivated human resources play an important and fundamental role in increasing the effectiveness of any organization. Many factors need to be considered when it comes to human resource welfare. One of the key factors in this area is job satisfaction. Government agencies operate in a complex environment with increasing demand. In such an environment, many factors can increase or decrease people's job communication satisfaction. Today, organizations find themselves in situations where the tendency toward entrepreneurial activities is essential. Therefore, organizations should create conditions in which the atmosphere and spirit of entrepreneurship prevails and individuals can engage in entrepreneurial activities of the organization individually and in groups. Entrepreneurial orientation is a strategic advantage that is realized in the study of opportunities and organizes these affairs in order to take advantage of these opportunities.

Keywords: Organizational characteristics, knowledge management infrastructure, job communication satisfaction, entrepreneurial orientation.

¹ Corresponding author's Email: marjanmoosavi@yahoo.com

Introduction

Job communication satisfaction is a vital scope in organizational characteristics. Government agencies operate in a complex environment with increasing demands. In such an environment, many factors can increase or decrease people's job communication satisfaction (Yılmaz et al., 2014). The management should consider the individuals' job communication satisfaction with regard to the important role of this issue in determining employees' behavior, defining their individual performance and their overall performance. Job communication satisfaction is therefore an essential factor in organizational behavior that must be understood and monitored. Organizations, in turn, must consider their employees' job communication satisfaction, because only satisfied employees will be motivated and productive. To this end, organizations should provide the necessary organizational resources and support for them (Bakotic, 2012).

(Lambert & Paoline, 2008) examined the effect of organizational characteristics on employees' job communication satisfaction and organizational commitment. Organizational characteristics in their studies included communication, formality, decision inputs, and promotion opportunities. In addition, the discussion on the determinants of employee job satisfaction in the literature revolves around three broad factors, namely, organizational, environmental and personal factors (Oluwunmi et al., 2017). The organizational factors examined in this research include salary, reward, promotion, Job security and organizational policies.

Knowledge management is often about creating, providing, strengthening and supporting appropriate knowledge environments in the organization to motivate and empower knowledge people to use and share their knowledge and create new knowledge (Kianto et al., 2016). In addition, those known in government organizations as knowledge employees, are those whose work is based on knowledge gained through formal education or work experience. Relying on their competencies and abilities to solve challenging problems and offer new solutions, they contribute to the growth and development of their organizations. This is where the knowledge management infrastructure comes into play.

Knowledge management infrastructure is the basis of knowledge management and reflects the culture and the structure of an organization, information technology infrastructure of the organization, shared knowledge and its physical environment (Pannu, 2017). Unfortunately, many organizations are not able to extricate knowledge and share it, because inefficient methods and inadequate infrastructure are used for knowledge management. Creating an appropriate infrastructure by adopting an appropriate culture and structure that improves interaction, creates a closer relationship among employees and encourages them to share and disseminate knowledge, and promotes the level of knowledge sharing and dissemination in organizations (Chow & Chan, 2008). (Gupta & Dutta, 2018) emphasized that the entrepreneurial characteristics and entrepreneurial culture of the organization (which are characterized by organizational values, unique concepts, and key organizational characteristics) constitute its entrepreneurial orientation. This issue has two aspects: a new way to implement and think and explore opportunities; and organizing resources to offer new prices to the market.

The present study attempts to investigate the effect of organizational characteristics, knowledge management infrastructure and entrepreneurial orientation on job communication satisfaction among employees of Iran's Atieh Sazan Hafez Company. Job communication satisfaction among the employees of this company is a must because it ultimately leads to higher levels of performance and increased productivity. On the other hand, knowledge management has not been seriously considered in this organization. This study helps the organization in planning knowledge management strategies and maximizing its benefits by identifying the impact of knowledge management infrastructure on employee's job communication satisfaction. Considering that the present study has been studied and analyzed in Atieh Sazan Hafez Insurance Company, the results of studies conducted with regard to the theoretical foundations and empirical background of the research show that so far, such a study has not been conducted in insurance companies. Therefore, considering the importance of the existence of this type of companies in Iran, it is possible to distinguish this issue from other studies, as well as the new and innovative aspect of this study.

In the knowledge-based economy, intellectual capital plays a vital role in increasing the value of organizations so that they will be able to be successful if they manage intellectual capital, effectively. In addition, one of the important capabilities of an organization that can greatly help other organizations in creating and dividing knowledge and create a "sustainable organizational advantage" for them compared to other organizations, is social capital. Today, knowledge is becoming a decisive factor in businesses' success. Since knowledge is considered as the most strategic organizational resource, organizations are faced with the basic question of how they can manage efficiently and effectively organizational knowledge in order to benefit from its advantages to advance the strategic goals of that organization. Its knowledge and management will be completely meaningless and without value apart from the strategic goals of the organization. Therefore, the knowledge management of the organization should be aligned and coordinated into consideration in line with the strategic actions of the organization in recent decades, knowledge has been known as one of the most crucial, vital, and strategic organizational resources, that lead to creative and effective method to increase innovation, reduce costs, improve decision-making, and create sustainable competition for organizations. Knowledge management refers to all efforts to obtain and use knowledge resources as much as possible. The successful accomplishment of knowledge management depends on choosing the best processes and determining the appropriate implementation strategy.

Our purpose is to provide a phase system to determine the strategy of knowledge management implementation in the organization according to the prioritized processes effective on the organization's knowledge management.

The basis of the proposed solution is based on the alignment of knowledge management processes and strategies to determine the appropriate strategy for implementing knowledge management in the organization. Considering that the values of some factors affecting the organization's knowledge management strategy formulation are qualitative.

In the unstable environmental conditions of organizations and the intensification of competitive methods, achieving new practical advantages and creating special capabilities is the main condition to overtake competitors, and this issue depends on the quality of knowledge and innovative capital of organizations. Knowledge management in customer-oriented companies and organizations is becoming a prerequisite that is necessary to create competition. Considering the importance of customers in today's competitive world, especially in industrial marketing, companies must have a correct understanding of customer needs. Today, more attention is paid to the created knowledge, relying on the understanding of the customer's needs, as an important factor of competitiveness in the global economy. Therefore, companies are looking for the main element of understanding the customer. On the other hand, since the customer is a key member in achieving the organization's goals, it is necessary to give more importance to the customer's knowledge. Therefore, the need to manage customer knowledge is a challenge that the organization must face. Customer knowledge management is related to acquiring, sharing and expanding customer knowledge with the ultimate goal of increase subscription between customers and the organization.

In this article, the approach of knowledge management and understanding customer needs and its relationship with knowledge management and customer relationship management have been discussed.

One of the important strategies of knowledge management is creating work spaces that create and share knowledge, learning, and change in organizations. On the one hand, the expansion of information and communication technology tools and web 2 tools has provided a platform for the formation of a new type of work space, as a virtual work space, which causes collaboration and sharing of best practices and proficient advancement in the organization. The speed of changes and transformations, competition, informed and wise customers and increasing innovations, challenges and uncertainties are facing organizations in the future, which proves the necessity of paying special attention to the subject of knowledge management and its adaptation to future conditions. If we do not have a forward-looking view in the progress of knowledge management in an organization, the developmental measures of knowledge management will not be beneficial based on the knowledge needs of the future, in addition to the inability to solve the problem.

Both concepts of future research and knowledge management are about identifying the complexity and dynamics arising from the internal and external environment of organizations and address the knowledge requirement of managers to make decisions in such environments.

Literature Review

Job communication satisfaction has attracted a lot of attention over the years, because employees are the main determinants of an organization's productivity. However, employees face various problems due to the changing and complex conditions of their environment. Employees with anxiety, depression or dissatisfaction show less quality and productivity at work (George & Zakkariya, 2015). By considering technology, culture and structure as knowledge management infrastructures, (Laupase, 2003) adopted a three-factor approach in order to assess capabilities of knowledge management and organizational effectiveness through data collected from senior executives.

(Lee & Choi, 2003) defined technology as the presence of information technology support in the organization. Technology capability refers to the basic structure of an organization's information technology, which includes hardware, software, network and internal and external databases (Pandey & Dutta, 2013). (Limbu et al., 2014) showed that there is a considerable relationship between technology and job satisfaction.

Organizational structure is the formal assignment of tasks and management mechanisms to maintain the alignment and integrity of work activities (Ghani et al., 2002). Organizational structure plays an important role in determining knowledge sharing and consequently employees' behavior and satisfaction and has a great impact on the use of technology, communication networks, facilitating participation and knowledge sharing in organizations (Pandey & Dutta, 2013). Assuming the presence of knowledge, (Hurley & Green, 2005) showed that reward, which is a critical structural factor, affects employees' behavior and decisions. Based on this, it is evident that the relationship between knowledge management structure and job communication satisfaction is significant.

Culture refers to the values, beliefs, principles, and behaviors that exist in an organization (Chou et al., 2011). According to (Farrell & Mavondo, 2004), the individuals' behavior in an organization is formed and controlled by organizational culture. (Lund, 2003) shows culture and job communication satisfaction have a positive and strong relationship.

In another study, (Magnier- Watanabe & Senoo, 2009) investigated the effect of culture and organizational characteristics on knowledge management. This study proved that the relationship between organizational characteristics and knowledge management is stronger than the relationship between organizational characteristics and culture. Therefore, there is a meaningful relationship between organizational characteristics and knowledge management and consequently knowledge management infrastructure.

According to (Delgado-Castro & Sánchez, 2019), entrepreneurial orientation is an innovative process in which new product and service opportunities are approved and created to produce more capabilities in order to provide new capital. The types of entrepreneurial activities that an organization pursues are often influenced by internal organizational factors (Burgelman, 1983). As a result, there is a positive and direct relationship between organizational characteristics and entrepreneurial orientation. Many studies have shown that employees' performance increases as their satisfaction improves.

However, little research has been done on the effect of entrepreneurial orientation on employees' job communication satisfaction. Nevertheless, (Adonisi, 2005) showed that relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and job communication satisfaction is significant.

Hypotheses and Conceptual Framework

Research Hypotheses

- H₁:** There is a relationship between organizational characteristics and technology.
- H₂:** There is a relationship between organizational characteristics and structure.
- H₃:** There is a relationship between organizational characteristics and culture.
- H₄:** There is a relationship between organizational characteristics and entrepreneurial orientation.
- H₅:** There is a relationship between technology and job communication satisfaction.
- H₆:** There is a relationship between structure and job communication satisfaction.
- H₇:** There is a relationship between culture and job communication satisfaction.
- H₈:** There is a relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and job communication satisfaction.
- H₉:** There is a relationship between organizational characteristics and job communication satisfaction

Figure 1. shows the conceptual model of present study, which presents the relationship between the research's variables.

Figure 1. Conceptual Model of the Research

Methodology

This research is a case study conducted at Iran's Atieh Sazan Hafez Company, which was purposefully selected and has 102 employees. This organization consists of 4 offices in Tehran. All 102 employees were selected for the study. Questionnaires were distributed offline among respondents. Given the support of the organization's management from this research, it was expected that this approach could achieve the maximum number of respondents. In order to avoid lost data, all questions were considered mandatory, so that all received answers could be used for analysis. The questionnaire generally included 98 questions in 7 main areas: 1) personal and organizational information, 2) organizational characteristics 3) technology, 4) structure, 5) culture, 6) entrepreneurial orientation and 7) job communication satisfaction. Questions related to each of these areas can be seen in Figure 1. Respondents also followed up to improve the response rate in order to ensure the generalizability of the research findings (Rea & Parker, 2005). A summary of the results regarding the demographic information of the participants is given in Table (1).

Table 1. Frequency and Percentage of Frequency of Demographic and General Information

Demographic and General Information	Category	Frequency	Percentage of Frequency
Gender	Male	35	34.4
	Female	67	65.6
Age	Less than 25	23	22.6
	25 to 35	57	55.8
	More than 35	22	21.6
Education	Diploma or lower	11	10.8
	Bachelor	54	52.9
	Master	28	27.5
	PhD	9	8.8
Job Title	Employee	91	89.2
	Manager	11	10.8
Working Experience	Less than 10 years	28	27.4
	10 to 20 years	59	57.9
	More than 20 years	15	14.7

The test tools as well as the relevant metrics used in this study were taken from previous studies. Organizational characteristics structural testing tools were taken from the article by (Hornsby et al., 1999). This structure consisted of 21 options. On the other hand, the test tools of (Covin & Slevin, 1989) and (Seibert et al., 2001) used for measurement the structure of entrepreneurial orientation, and the total number of options used for this structure was 23. Test tools and metrics developed by (Lee & Choi, 2003) utilized to measure the structure of knowledge management infrastructure. This structure used 26 options that covered the entire dimension of this structure. A Questionnaire was used to measure job communication satisfaction, which was developed by (Sharma, 2015) and included 28 questions in this area. Because behavior measurement can be best measured with a point Likert spectrum (Baker et al., 2010), respondents' answers to the test options were scored from 1 (very disagree) to 5 (very agree).

This study uses the partial least squares method (Wold, 1975) Structural Equation Modeling, and Smart PLS software is used according to the sample size and number of variables. The main idea of the partial least squares method is to first estimate the weight relations connecting a latent variable to its components and then to calculate the factor loads of each latent variable using weight relations based on the weighted average of its components and finally to use these factor loads to estimate parameters for structural relationships in sets of regression equations (Chin, 1998). Thus, first, the relationships between the existing measurement models are ensured using the reliability and validity criteria, and then the relationships in the structural part are examined and interpreted.

Results

After collecting data for a month, almost all employees of the organization answered the questionnaires completely. Due to the mandatory response to all questions, no

questionnaire was deleted due to missing data. After data collection, a response rate of more than 98% was obtained. This response rate was sufficient for statistical analysis (Krejcie & Morgan, 1970).

The reliability of test tools should be considered to improve the validity of research findings. According to (Borg & Gall, 1979), the transparency of questions in the data collection process must be ensured. To ensure the reliability of the test instruments, a reliability test was performed for all the structures under study. Cronbach's alpha for each area of the questionnaire and the whole questionnaire was a above 0.7 that was sufficient to support the reliability of the test instruments and to ensure the validity of the research findings (DeVellis, 1991). Table (2) lists Cronbach's alpha values for each of the questionnaire areas separately.

Table 2. Reliability Indicators

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha Values
Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.907
Job Communication Satisfaction	0.957
Structure	0.772
Culture	0.913
Technology	0.875
Organizational Characteristics	0.907

First, the conceptual model of the research was fully implemented and according to the results, the indicators that had a factor load of less than 0.5 or a t-statistic of less than 1.96 were removed, and the modified model was re-implemented. Results are indicated in Figures (2) and (3).

In order to analyze the structure of the questionnaire and discover the factors that make up each structure, factor loads have been used. The results of factor loading of research variables are summarized in the above figures. All values of factor loads are greater than 0.5, and the calculated values of t for each of the factor loads are more than 1.96 (at a significance level of less than 0.05). Therefore, the alignment of the questionnaire questions to measure the concepts can be shown at this point. The results of factor analysis showed that all indicators related to each of the areas of the questionnaire have acceptable t values (more than 1.96) and factor loads (more than 0.5) and were considered suitable indicators for job satisfaction.

Figure 2. The Structural Equation Model in Path Coefficient Estimation

Figure 3. The Structural Equation Model in the Significant State of Coefficients

Table 3. Path Coefficients and T-statistics (Predictive Variable: Organizational Characteristics)

Dependent Variables	Path Coefficients	t-statistics
Technology	0.584	8.129
Structure	0.707	17.571
Culture	0.648	12.317
Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.476	4.616

According to Table (3), based on the amount of path coefficient, which is 0.584 and the amount of t-statistic with a value of 8.129, it is evident that there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational characteristics and technology at 99% confidence level. Therefore, hypothesis H1 is significant and is confirmed.

According to the amount of path coefficient (0.707) and the amount of t-statistic with a value of 17.571, there is a positive and meaningful relationship between organizational characteristics and structure at 99% confidence level. Therefore, the second hypothesis is confirmed. Considering the path coefficient of 0.648 and t-statistic with a value of 12.317, it can be said that there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational characteristics and culture at 99% confidence level. Therefore, hypothesis is confirmed. Considering the path coefficient of 0.476 and t-statistic with a value of 4.616, it can be said that there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational characteristics and entrepreneurial orientation at 99% confidence level. Therefore, hypothesis H4 is significant and is confirmed.

Table 4. Path Coefficients and T-statistics (Dependent Variable: Job Communication Satisfaction)

Predictive Variables	Path Coefficients	t-statistics
Technology	0.103	1.094
Structure	0.072	0.692
Culture	0.294	2.539
Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.009	0.065
Organizational Characteristics	0.485	3.827

According to Table (4), by considering the path coefficient of 0.103 and t-statistic with a value of 1.094, it is evident that at 95% confidence level, there is no significant relationship between technology and job satisfaction. Therefore, hypothesis 5 is not significant and is not confirmed. According to the amount of path coefficient, which is at 0.072 and the amount of t-statistic with a value of 0.692, there is no significant relationship between structure and job satisfaction at 95% confidence level. Therefore, hypothesis H6 of the research is not significant and is not confirmed.

The amount of path coefficient ,0.294, and the amount of t-statistic with a value of 2.539, there is a positive and significant relationship between culture and job satisfaction at 95% confidence level. Therefore, hypothesis H7 is significant and is confirmed. Based on the path coefficient, which is 0.009 and t-statistic with a value of 0.065, the results

indicate that at 95% confidence level, there is no meaningful relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and job communication satisfaction. Therefore, hypothesis H8 is not significant and is not confirmed. Considering the path coefficient of 0.485 and t-statistic with a value of 4.827, it can be said that there is a positive and significant relationship between organizational characteristics and job communication satisfaction at 99% confidence level. Therefore, hypothesis H9 is significant and is confirmed.

Table 5. The Results of the Criterion R^2

Structures	R^2
Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.227
Job Communication Satisfaction	0.697
Structure	0.500
Culture	0.420
Technology	0.341

Table 6. The Results of the Criterion Q^2 of the Endogenous Structures

Structures	Q^2
Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.137
Job Communication Satisfaction	0.307
Structure	0.208
Culture	0.205
Technology	0.210

Criteria R^2 and Q^2

The criterion R^2 is used for examining the fit of a structural model in a research, and the coefficients of R^2 are related to endogenous (dependent) latent variables of the model. R^2 is a criterion that shows the impact of an exogenous variable and an endogenous variable, and the values of 0.19, 0.32 and 0.67, respectively, are considered as the owner for the weak, medium and strong for it (Chin, 1988). The results of the criterion R^2 for the structures of this research are indicated in the table (5).

The Criterion Q^2 also determines the predictive power of a model and if the value for an endogenous structure achieves three values of 0.02, 0.15 and 0.35, it indicates the weak, medium and strong predictive power of the related exogenous structures. The results of Table 6 show the appropriate predictive power of this model regarding the endogenous structures of the research and confirm the appropriate fit of the structural model.

Redundancy Criterion

The redundancy criterion is an indicator of the quality of a structural model for each endogenous variable according to its measurement model. This criterion analyzed through multiplying the common values of the structures by their corresponding R^2 values and indicates the amount of variation of the indicators of an endogenous structure that is

influenced by one or more exogenous structures. The higher the amount of redundancy is, the better the structural part of the model in a study is compatible.

Table 7. The Results of the Redundancy of the Endogenous Structures

Structures	R ²	Communality	Redundancy
Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.227	0.505	0.114
Job Communication Satisfaction	0.697	0.504	0.351
Structure	0.500	0.559	0.279
Culture	0.420	0.557	0.233
Technology	0.341	0.668	0.227
The Total Amount of Redundancy			0.241

Goodness of Fit Criterion

The goodness of fit criterion (GoF) depends on the general part of the structural equation models. This means that by examining the fit of the measurement and structural part of the research, the fit of the general part can also be controlled through this criterion (Tennhaus et al., 2004). For this criterion, the values 0.01, 0.25 and 0.36 are represented as weak, medium and strong, respectively. Considering that the value obtained for the goodness of fit index (0.490) is greater than 0.36 so that the present model has a strong fit.

Table 8. The Results of R² and Communality

Structures	R ²	Communality
Entrepreneurial Orientation	0.227	0.505
Job Communication Satisfaction	0.697	0.504
Structure	0.500	0.559
Culture	0.420	0.557
Technology	0.341	0.668
Organizational Characteristics	-	0.511
GoF	0.437	0.437
	0.490	

Discussion and Conclusion

This research tested four hypotheses to examine the relationship of organizational characteristics and knowledge management infrastructure with entrepreneurial orientation, four hypotheses to examine the relationship of knowledge management infrastructure and entrepreneurial orientation with job communication satisfaction and one hypothesis to examine the relationship between organizational characteristics and employees' job communication satisfaction. Based on the statistical analysis, six hypotheses were confirmed, but the hypotheses related to technology and job communication satisfaction, structure and job communication satisfaction, as well as entrepreneurial orientation and job communication satisfaction were not confirmed.

The first, second and third hypotheses of the study were confirmed. These hypotheses were about the correlation between organizational characteristics and knowledge management infrastructure. (Baskaran, 2018) indicated that organizational characteristics affect technology, structure and culture as knowledge management enablers, positively. (Zahra & Nielsen, 2002) also showed that technology can improve group coordination because it leads employees to solve problems collaboratively.

The fourth hypothesis of the study (the relationship between organizational characteristics and entrepreneurial orientation) was confirmed. This issue is also in line with Baskaran's (2018) research which shows the relationship between organizational characteristics and entrepreneurial orientation mediated by knowledge management enablers.

The fifth hypothesis (the relationship between technology and job communication satisfaction) was not confirmed. Contrary to the results of this study, the results of previous research show that providing such tools to employees makes their tasks easier in the organization and increases communication satisfaction. When the organization invests in technology, it affects the employees' perception of the organization and improves their job communication satisfaction. The reason for the contradiction between the results obtained in this study and previous research is the lack of knowledge of the managers of the organization under study about the relevant technologies and, as a result, the lack of attention to employees familiar with those technologies, which discourages them from using the technology.

The sixth hypothesis of the study (the relationship between structure and job communication satisfaction) was not confirmed, though studies conducted by (Willem et al., 2007) and (Kessler, 2007) showed the opposite and concluded that organizational structure has a positive effect on employees' job communication satisfaction. The reason for the alignment of these results with the results of other similar research is that they have been conducted in the developing countries. Like the present research, these researches have also been done in a hierarchical structure, while the studies that are inconsistent with the present study have been conducted in an organization with a non-hierarchical structure.

The seventh research hypothesis (the relationship between culture and job communication satisfaction) was confirmed. This is also consistent with the results of some previous research. Researchers such as (Silverthorne, 2004), (Bellou, 2010), (Boerebach et al., 2012) and (Masum et al., 2015) obtained similar results. On the other hand, some other research found that there is no relationship between culture and job communication satisfaction (Sabri et al., 2011). This may be due to the cultural differences among the countries studied by the researchers.

The eighth research hypothesis (the relationship between entrepreneurial orientation and job communication satisfaction) was not confirmed. This is contrary to the findings of previous research such as those conducted by (Giordani, 2008), (Callaghan, 2009), (Sriprasert, 2013) and (Sajeva & Rybakovas, 2011) which showed that entrepreneurial orientation has a positive effect on job communication satisfaction. This contradiction is also due to the level of importance given by the organizations to the entrepreneurial spirit

in performing tasks. Previously studied organizations paid special attention to this issue, but the organization studied in this research only emphasizes on performing defined tasks and does not give much value to entrepreneurial orientation.

The ninth hypothesis (the relationship between organizational characteristics and job communication satisfaction) was confirmed. This issue was also confirmed in the research by (Lambert & Paoline, 2008). In addition, (Currivan, 1999), (McGivern & Tvorik, 1997) and (Lund, 2003) demonstrated the existence of a meaningful relationship between the various dimensions of organizational characteristics and job communication satisfaction. Finally, the final model of the research after rejecting the relevant hypotheses is as follows:

Figure 4. The Final Conceptual Model of Research

In short, organizational characteristics improve the quality of all aspects of knowledge management infrastructure in the organization and also increase the entrepreneurial orientation in the behavior of employees. Dimensions of knowledge management infrastructure can also affect employee's job communication satisfaction. Satisfaction with business relationships is important at all levels of an organization. However, providing such satisfaction to employees depends on the availability of various dimensions of knowledge management infrastructure and the organization's capability to provide such satisfaction to employees. Based on the studies performed and empirical evidence presented in this study, cultural aspect of knowledge management infrastructure is very important to create job communication satisfaction in employees. In addition, organizational characteristics themselves are effective in increasing job communication satisfaction, though entrepreneurial orientation does not play an effective role in increasing job communication satisfaction based on the results of the present study.

Due to time constraints, this study focused only on Iran's Atieh Sazan Hafez Company. Applying the results of this research in the strategy of knowledge management promotes evaluation and improvement of job satisfaction of experts and managers of Atieh Sazan Hafez Company and ultimately improves the evaluation of the whole organization. Data analysis using structural equation method measures all knowledge management infrastructures, employees' job satisfaction and entrepreneurial orientation of the organization and presenting such indicators and methods improves the attitude of managers in evaluating the organization's knowledge management and employees' job satisfaction.

According to the framework and findings of this study, the following suggestions are presented as guidelines for future research:

1- Knowledge management infrastructure is considered one of the effective factors in promoting job satisfaction and job communication. Thus, in future research, appropriate knowledge management infrastructure can be examined to properly lead to increased job satisfaction and job communication;

2- In future research, we can consider the neglected variables in the study of organizational characteristics, knowledge management infrastructure, entrepreneurial orientation and job communication satisfaction, and examine their interaction with each other in detail. This may lead to the discovery of more findings;

3- The model presented in this research can be tested in other environments such as private offices or even other countries to ensure the generalization of the findings.

In the continuation of this research, some suggestions can be presented in the applied fields:

1- In order to create a suitable environment for the accomplishment of knowledge management system and thus improve the performance of the organization, it is suggested to provide the necessary conditions for continuous training and learning of employees. Creating the culture of organizations that encourages creativity and innovation of

employees will also improve the performance of knowledge management and thus improve job satisfaction.

2- Considering that the implementation of knowledge management in the organization is significantly dependent on the support from senior managers in providing its infrastructure such as culture and technology, it is therefore suggested that the managers of the organization consider this seriously through various methods, including active participation in various stages of the knowledge management implementation process, supporting the distribution and sharing of knowledge in the organization and involving the level of knowledge performance of individuals in performance evaluation systems.

3- Considering that technology is an important component in the knowledge management infrastructure, developing and strengthening the necessary technical infrastructures such as network communication, citation management, search engines and information retrieval databases and, integrating and updating the organization's information systems, facilitating employees' access to knowledge and information related to their field of work by using new information and communication technologies, etc. are among other suggestions that can improve the process of implementing knowledge management and thus improve organizational performance and increase job communication satisfaction.

References

- Adonisi, M. (2005). *The relationship between corporate entrepreneurship, market orientation, organisational flexibility and job satisfaction* University of Pretoria].
- Baker, L. R., Stephens, F., & Hitchcock, L. (2010). Social work practitioners and practice evaluation: How are we doing? *Journal of Human Behavior in the Social Environment*, 20(8), 963-973.
- Bakotic, D. (2012). Job satisfaction of knowledge workers in Croatian companies. *The Journal of International Management Studies*, 7(2), 53-60.
- Baskaran, S. (2018). Mediation effect of knowledge management enablers on the relationship between organizational characteristics and entrepreneurial orientation. *Gadjah Mada International Journal of Business*, 20(1), 1-32.
- Bellou, V. (2010). Organizational culture as a predictor of job satisfaction: the role of gender and age. *Career development international*.
- Boerebach, B. C., Lombarts, K. M., Keijzer, C., Heineman, M. J., & Arah, O. A. (2012). The teacher, the physician and the person: how faculty's teaching performance influences their role modelling. *PloS one*, 7(3), e32089.
- Borg, W. R., & Gall, M. (1979). Educational Research: An Introduction to Research. In: London: Longman.
- Burgelman, R. A. (1983). Corporate entrepreneurship and strategic management: Insights from a process study. *Management science*, 29(12), 1349-1364.

- Callaghan, C. W. (2009). *Entrepreneurial orientation and entrepreneurial performance of central Johannesburg informal sector street traders* University of the Witwatersrand].
- Chin, W. W. (1998). The partial least squares approach to structural equation modeling. *Modern methods for business research*, 295(2), 295-336.
- Chou, Y.-C., Fu, L.-y., Kröger, T., & Ru-Yan, C. (2011). Job satisfaction and quality of life among home care workers: a comparison of home care workers who are and who are not informal carers. *International Psychogeriatrics*, 23(5), 814-825.
- Chow, W. S., & Chan, L. S. (2008). Social network, social trust and shared goals in organizational knowledge sharing. *Information & management*, 45(7), 458-465.
- Covin, J. G., & Slevin, D. P. (1989). Strategic management of small firms in hostile and benign environments. *Strategic management journal*, 10(1), 75-87.
- Currivan, D. B. (1999). The causal order of job satisfaction and organizational commitment in models of employee turnover. *Human resource management review*, 9(4), 495-524.
- Delgado-Castro, C. G., & Sánchez, H. V. V. (2019). Social Innovation and social entrepreneurship: Bibliographic Review. *Revista Científica FIPCAEC (Fomento de la investigación y publicación en Ciencias Administrativas, Económicas y Contables)*. ISSN: 2588-090X. *Polo de Capacitación, Investigación y Publicación (POCAIP)*, 4(4), 486-509.
- DeVellis, R. (1991). Scale development. Newbery Park. In: CA: Sage.
- Farrell, M., & Mavondo, F. T. (2004). The effect of downsizing strategy and reorientation strategy on a learning orientation. *Personnel Review*.
- George, E., & Zakkariya, K. (2015). Job related stress and job satisfaction: a comparative study among bank employees. *Journal of Management Development*.
- Ghani, K. A., Jayabalan, V., & Sugumar, M. (2002). Impact of advanced manufacturing technology on organizational structure. *The Journal of High Technology Management Research*, 13(2), 157-175.
- Giordani, L. G. (2008). Entrepreneurial Orientation and Subjective Well-being: a Comparison of Employed and Self-Employed Motivation and Commitment (Summary). *Frontiers of Entrepreneurship Research*, 28(4), 8.
- Gupta, V. K., & Dutta, D. K. (2018). The rich legacy of Covin and Slevin (1989) and Lumpkin and Dess (1996): A constructive critical analysis of their deep impact on entrepreneurial orientation research. In *Foundational research in entrepreneurship studies* (pp. 155-177). Springer.

- Hornsby, J. S., Kuratko, D. F., & Montagno, R. V. (1999). Perception of internal factors for corporate entrepreneurship: A comparison of Canadian and US managers. *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 24(2), 9-24.
- Hurley, T. A., & Green, C. W. (2005). Knowledge management and the nonprofit industry: A within and between approach. *Journal of Knowledge Management Practice*, 6(1), 1-10.
- Kessler, S. R. (2007). The effects of organizational structure on faculty job performance, job satisfaction, and counterproductive work behavior.
- Kianto, A., Vanhala, M., & Heilmann, P. (2016). The impact of knowledge management on job satisfaction. *Journal of knowledge management*.
- Krejcie, R. V., & Morgan, D. W. (1970). Determining sample size for research activities. *Educational and psychological measurement*, 30(3), 607-610.
- Lambert, E. G., & Paoline, E. A. (2008). The influence of individual, job, and organizational characteristics on correctional staff job stress, job satisfaction, and organizational commitment. *Criminal Justice Review*, 33(4), 541-564.
- Laupase, R. (2003). The process of converting consultants' tacit knowledge to organisational explicit knowledge: Case studies in management consulting firms. In *Knowledge Management: Current Issues and Challenges* (pp. 212-225). IGI Global.
- Lee, H., & Choi, B. (2003). Knowledge management enablers, processes, and organizational performance: An integrative view and empirical examination. *Journal of management information systems*, 20(1), 179-228.
- Limbu, Y. B., Jayachandran, C., & Babin, B. J. (2014). Does information and communication technology improve job satisfaction? The moderating role of sales technology orientation. *Industrial Marketing Management*, 43(7), 1236-1245.
- Lund, D. B. (2003). Organizational culture and job satisfaction. *Journal of Business & Industrial Marketing*.
- Magnier- Watanabe, R., & Senoo, D. (2009). Congruent knowledge management behaviors as discriminate sources of competitive advantage. *Journal of Workplace Learning*.
- Masum, A. K. M., Azad, M. A. K., & Beh, L.-S. (2015). Determinants of academics' job satisfaction: Empirical evidence from private universities in Bangladesh. *PloS one*, 10(2), e0117834.
- McGivern, M. H., & Tvorik, S. J. (1997). Determinants of organizational performance. *Management Decision*.

- Oluwunmi, A., Emeghe, I., Oluwadamilola, A., Fulani, O., Peter, N., & Akinjare, O. (2017). Gender inequality and women discrimination in real estate firms in Lagos State, Nigeria.
- Pandey, S. C., & Dutta, A. (2013). Role of knowledge infrastructure capabilities in knowledge management. *Journal of knowledge management*.
- Pannu, H. (2017). The impact of knowledge management infrastructure on organizational performance in SMEs. *International Journal of Human Resource & Industrial Research*, 4(2), 26-31.
- Sabri, P. S. U., Ilyas, M., & Amjad, Z. (2011). Organizational culture and its impact on the job satisfaction of the University teachers of Lahore. *International Journal of Business and Social Science*, 2(24).
- Sajeva, S., & Rybakovas, E. (2011). The relationship between social entrepreneurship and subjective well-being. *Proceeding of EBRF*.
- Seibert, S. E., Kraimer, M. L., & Liden, R. C. (2001). A social capital theory of career success. *Academy of management journal*, 44(2), 219-237.
- Sharma, P. R. (2015). *Organizational communication: Perceptions of staff members' level of communication satisfaction and job satisfaction* [East Tennessee State University].
- Silverthorne, C. (2004). The impact of organizational culture and person- organization fit on organizational commitment and job satisfaction in Taiwan. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*.
- Sriprasert, P. (2013). The effect of entrepreneurial orientation on the success of community enterprise: A study of Nakhon Si Thammarat, Thailand. *International Proceedings of Economics Development and Research*, 59, 158.
- Willem, A., Buelens, M., & De Jonghe, I. (2007). Impact of organizational structure on nurses' job satisfaction: A questionnaire survey. *International journal of nursing studies*, 44(6), 1011-1020.
- Wold, H. (1975). Path models with latent variables: The NIPALS approach. In *Quantitative sociology* (pp. 307-357). Elsevier.
- Yılmaz, S. M., Çelebi, Ç. D., & Çakmak, E. (2014). Job satisfaction level of academicians in faculty of education. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 116, 1021-1025.
- Zahra, S. A., & Nielsen, A. P. (2002). Sources of capabilities, integration and technology commercialization. *Strategic management journal*, 23(5), 377-398.

COPYRIGHTS

©2022 The author(s). This is an open access article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0), which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, as long as the original authors and source are cited. No permission is required from the authors or the publishers.

HOW TO CITE THIS ARTICLE

Mousavi, M. (2022). Examining the Relationship between Organizational Characteristics, Knowledge Management Infrastructure and Entrepreneurial Orientation with Job Communication Satisfaction. *International Journal of Management, Accounting and Economics*, 9(9), 594-615.

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7180177

URL: https://www.ijmae.com/article_158737.html

